

Circle packing inside a regular tridecagon: supplemental material

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Abstract

We report the configurations of $2 \leq N \leq 200$ congruent disks packed inside a regular tridecagon obtained using the algorithms of ref. [1].

1 Introduction

We report here the densest configurations for circle packing inside a regular tridecagon that we have found using the algorithms described in ref. [1] for $2 \leq N \leq 200$. Although we cannot claim that these configurations correspond to global maxima of the packing fraction, they provide good lower bounds to the packing fraction. Such bounds may be improved in the future, either by performing more intensive numerical calculations or by coming up with more efficient algorithms. The reader should refer to [1] for a description of the algorithms and a discussion of previous work.

This document is organized as follows: in section 2 we display the densest configurations of N congruent disks packed inside a regular tridecagon, for $2 \leq N \leq 200$; in section 3 we display the Voronoi diagrams for the configurations previously found. The data corresponding to the configurations reported in this document may be found at the repository [2] or directly from the author.

2 Densest configurations found for $N \leq 200$

The configurations are plotted assigning a color code described in [1], which depends on the number of contacts of each disk. Since the calculation is numerical, this information has to be assessed within a given tolerance: in our case, if the distance between two disks exceed by 10^{-6} the minimal distance among any two disks in the configuration, they are regarded as being in contact. Refinement is typically a slow process and it could be demanding when N is large:

configurations with a large number of black disks (i.e. disks that are not in contact with any other disk or with the walls of the container) are most likely improvable upon performing a suitable refinement.

Table 1: radii and density of the best packing configurations inside a regular tridecagon for $2 \leq N \leq 79$.

N	r	ρ	N	r	ρ
2	0.490852350956	0.50115715449	41	0.135458316081	0.782415399939
3	0.453721030611	0.642304940782	42	0.134201917313	0.786699582542
4	0.405005977913	0.682378046914	43	0.1321167914	0.780596643411
5	0.361832605105	0.680812609101	44	0.130778409815	0.782648882219
6	0.328528936971	0.673504800342	45	0.12957544058	0.785778407097
7	0.325795415063	0.772734254637	46	0.128357192201	0.788207270777
8	0.295713378243	0.727568889597	47	0.127001966463	0.788425999187
9	0.270713532032	0.685969218499	48	0.125742342096	0.789308021172
10	0.257507390176	0.689638633874	49	0.124498559526	0.789890556053
11	0.249350846232	0.711306154273	50	0.123377223444	0.791556969892
12	0.242636309602	0.734742257162	51	0.122237590994	0.792541347885
13	0.232022716624	0.727857824969	52	0.121155200719	0.793833924848
14	0.225977211465	0.743531743088	53	0.12015106394	0.795743865941
15	0.217182881887	0.735842098211	54	0.119485816955	0.801804819992
16	0.212526386682	0.751601932239	55	0.119043807976	0.810622210629
17	0.204556830817	0.739808101293	56	0.117510374377	0.804234380579
18	0.201313210227	0.758681059492	57	0.116582903587	0.805724888479
19	0.201215077473	0.800049447442	58	0.115482895896	0.804461961495
20	0.193410671799	0.778095763546	59	0.11418905756	0.800097985725
21	0.188968572537	0.779903102202	60	0.113443453389	0.803067990754
22	0.180958379158	0.749242258475	61	0.112782006612	0.80695934957
23	0.176958040459	0.749049684183	62	0.111607500518	0.803194344642
24	0.173642673118	0.752603711524	63	0.110568973583	0.801030944833
25	0.170506316818	0.755897907513	64	0.109773669017	0.802081542298
26	0.16825963534	0.765553282387	65	0.10885555958	0.801044742204
27	0.165751602815	0.771474233852	66	0.108155959015	0.802947275548
28	0.162843659376	0.772221565621	67	0.107351168653	0.803027733145
29	0.160247487817	0.774502182358	68	0.106736901099	0.805712832055
30	0.158083305832	0.779714232217	69	0.105853645986	0.804086779316
31	0.154803458236	0.772618670643	70	0.105268544265	0.806747192404
32	0.152521656106	0.774203608302	71	0.104514680429	0.80659426704
33	0.150798146734	0.780455483862	72	0.10371690058	0.805515209025
34	0.148380724393	0.778531302906	73	0.102853050666	0.803155066823
35	0.146487361215	0.781107025855	74	0.102170196755	0.803382500203
36	0.145124151092	0.78854062665	75	0.101528477977	0.804042866077
37	0.144398997547	0.802365540907	76	0.100842485013	0.803790481566
38	0.140947674923	0.785130081243	77	0.100195431709	0.803949473427
39	0.139180014681	0.785706871226	78	0.099550419467	0.803938782034
40	0.137832158268	0.790320583217	79	0.0990692507234	0.806393533048

Table 2: radii and density of the best packing configurations inside a regular tridecagon for $80 \leq N \leq 161$.

N	r	ρ	N	r	ρ
80	0.0985868715864	0.808668164707	121	0.0806699148409	0.818937494603
81	0.0981239795995	0.811105813417	122	0.0802814621815	0.817772621289
82	0.0975622899285	0.811745726965	123	0.0799566805909	0.817818276251
83	0.0968927456524	0.810406295286	124	0.0795971800615	0.817069948031
84	0.096440475047	0.812531405745	125	0.0793511927791	0.818576212063
85	0.096012107766	0.814916519736	126	0.0790602791598	0.819085844194
86	0.0953775356041	0.813641015303	127	0.0788263213093	0.820707548107
87	0.0947408209472	0.812149026649	128	0.0785544402137	0.821473643977
88	0.0941049254741	0.810493564069	129	0.0782752155509	0.822016325762
89	0.093455154455	0.808423098949	130	0.0779923076883	0.822411324709
90	0.0929504114162	0.808699790176	131	0.0776141971845	0.820721523855
91	0.0924685159671	0.809228846968	132	0.0773237600886	0.8208088848
92	0.0919747106327	0.809406850672	133	0.0771191138366	0.822655281449
93	0.0914531469861	0.808951427765	134	0.0768751474615	0.823604878215
94	0.0911298376398	0.811878863048	135	0.0765651058492	0.823071817143
95	0.0907207242793	0.813165250003	136	0.0763970826147	0.825533393386
96	0.0902508852256	0.813235562671	137	0.0761737517813	0.826748561969
97	0.0898335497256	0.814124912244	138	0.0757710054219	0.824000309264
98	0.0893751793311	0.814145667973	139	0.0754303372851	0.822524963893
99	0.0889034378635	0.813794018552	140	0.0751473213238	0.822237411003
100	0.0884786384561	0.814177413182	141	0.0749163103478	0.823026958809
101	0.0879802798363	0.813081800096	142	0.0746535009541	0.823058853819
102	0.0875604712595	0.813314547818	143	0.074410068532	0.823458344345
103	0.0871395576955	0.81341113886	144	0.074112770263	0.822603919474
104	0.0867854103838	0.814646076962	145	0.073925200032	0.824129019918
105	0.0864325425183	0.815804439331	146	0.0736605228653	0.8238812867
106	0.0859433384295	0.814277609093	147	0.0734129353429	0.82395729178
107	0.0855286104675	0.814045722584	148	0.073172091846	0.824128333246
108	0.0851071141844	0.813575146536	149	0.0729957647676	0.825702848064
109	0.0846567146777	0.812440392419	150	0.0728341314786	0.827567332334
110	0.0843014332274	0.813026665675	151	0.0726989051632	0.829993853994
111	0.0840715238492	0.815948983483	152	0.0725189004946	0.831358225136
112	0.0837701306268	0.817407458622	153	0.0723552768447	0.833055695881
113	0.0834670108959	0.818748191173	154	0.0721527551832	0.833813165206
114	0.0831643763803	0.820014836373	155	0.0718501091501	0.832201991685
115	0.0829068651594	0.822093125861	156	0.0716032978139	0.831826662142
116	0.082540580798	0.821930730804	157	0.0713297493282	0.830774650172
117	0.0821476557111	0.821142250326	158	0.0710565735712	0.829674606731
118	0.0817415986727	0.819993575914	159	0.0707642942412	0.828071183847
119	0.0813891560203	0.819827042401	160	0.0705489066365	0.828214340105
120	0.0810473096069	0.819786269343	161	0.0702730775078	0.82688670791

Table 3: radii and density of the best packing configurations inside a regular tridecagon for $162 \leq N \leq 200$.

N	r	ρ	N	r	ρ
162	0.0700992786668	0.827912235227	182	0.0662213149702	0.830059409298
163	0.0699098646274	0.828527093878	183	0.0660159503774	0.829451577871
164	0.0697829094518	0.830585186596	184	0.0658443100686	0.829653049853
165	0.0694562516407	0.827844592561	185	0.0656887212919	0.830224475384
166	0.0692290077333	0.827420906411	186	0.0654751646666	0.829293633092
167	0.0690108847359	0.827168237902	187	0.065346295985	0.83047343689
168	0.0688190686908	0.827502000245	188	0.065149833479	0.829901706285
169	0.0686362632614	0.828011093769	189	0.0650633223226	0.832101805034
170	0.068455102185	0.828519540731	190	0.06498121562	0.834394537526
171	0.0682411751738	0.828192499367	191	0.0647595483914	0.833073228817
172	0.0680792526933	0.82908717052	192	0.0645744009485	0.832653264004
173	0.067910970701	0.829789944619	193	0.0644019477505	0.832525417511
174	0.0677478632109	0.830582239863	194	0.0642893621717	0.833915703762
175	0.0675724851304	0.831036348428	195	0.0640910122089	0.833049984719
176	0.0674474199529	0.832694198358	196	0.0640046931825	0.835068111432
177	0.0672531358896	0.8326079121	197	0.0639014828733	0.836623938686
178	0.0670255469535	0.831654465715	198	0.0637242039719	0.836211655446
179	0.0667583969914	0.829673117934	199	0.0636351459371	0.838087481204
180	0.066592556799	0.830168160698	200	0.0634592552835	0.837649100144
181	0.0663993000009	0.829942041958			

Figure 1: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tridecagon ($2 \leq N \leq 13$).

Figure 2: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tridecagon ($14 \leq N \leq 25$).

Figure 3: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tridecagon ($26 \leq N \leq 37$).

Figure 4: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tridecagon ($38 \leq N \leq 49$).

Figure 5: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tridecagon ($50 \leq N \leq 61$).

Figure 6: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tridecagon ($62 \leq N \leq 73$).

Figure 7: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tridecagon ($74 \leq N \leq 85$).

Figure 8: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tridecagon ($86 \leq N \leq 97$).

Figure 9: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tridecagon ($98 \leq N \leq 109$).

Figure 10: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tridecagon ($110 \leq N \leq 121$).

Figure 11: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tridecagon ($122 \leq N \leq 133$).

Figure 12: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tridecagon ($134 \leq N \leq 145$).

Figure 13: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tridecagon ($146 \leq N \leq 157$).

Figure 14: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tridecagon ($158 \leq N \leq 169$).

Figure 15: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tridecagon ($170 \leq N \leq 181$).

Figure 16: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tridecagon ($182 \leq N \leq 193$).

Figure 17: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tridecagon ($194 \leq N \leq 200$).

3 Voronoi diagrams

We report the Voronoi diagrams for the configurations of section 2. We use the same color scheme as before, where the colors of each cell depends on the number of sides. One can assign a topological charge to the cell, depending on the number of sides of the cell and on the location of the cell: for internal cells, the topological charge is $q_{int} = 6 - \ell$, where ℓ is the number of sides, while for cells on the border $q_{border} = 5 - \ell$. Vertices from which emanate more than three lines carry a topological charge $q_{vert} = -2(n - 3)$, where n is the number of lines.

The Euler theorem of topology requires that the sum of all topological charges be equal to 6, regardless of the complexity of the configuration, but it does not forbid changing a number of cells with the same number of cells with different individual topological charges as long as the total charge is kept the same. For example, one could substitute two hexagonal internal cells with a pair consisting of pentagonal and heptagonal cells. See [1] for a more detailed discussion.

Figure 18: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tridecagon ($2 \leq N \leq 13$).

Figure 19: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tridecagon ($14 \leq N \leq 25$).

Figure 20: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tridecagon ($26 \leq N \leq 37$).

Figure 21: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tridecagon ($38 \leq N \leq 49$).

Figure 22: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tridecagon ($50 \leq N \leq 61$).

Figure 23: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tridecagon ($62 \leq N \leq 73$).

Figure 24: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tridecagon ($74 \leq N \leq 85$).

Figure 25: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tridecagon ($86 \leq N \leq 97$).

Figure 26: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tridecagon ($98 \leq N \leq 109$).

Figure 27: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tridecagon ($110 \leq N \leq 121$).

Figure 28: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tridecagon ($122 \leq N \leq 133$).

Figure 29: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tridecagon ($134 \leq N \leq 145$).

Figure 30: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tridecagon ($146 \leq N \leq 157$).

Figure 31: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tridecagon ($158 \leq N \leq 169$).

Figure 32: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tridecagon ($170 \leq N \leq 181$).

Figure 33: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tridecagon ($182 \leq N \leq 193$).

Figure 34: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular tridecagon ($194 \leq N \leq 200$).

References

- [1] Amore, Paolo. "Circle packing in regular polygons." arXiv preprint arXiv:2212.12287 (2022).
- [2] Paolo Amore, "Coordinates of the packing configurations of arXiv:2212.12287 ", <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7574070>